

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: IRELAND

Engagement of Citizen Science in Freshwater Data Collection

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In recent decades, although not a new concept, interest in the potential benefits of citizen science has grown rapidly in many fields and particularly in relation to freshwaters. So, do we as freshwater scientists and managers see a useful role for citizen science and how can we maximise the benefits for both scientists and the volunteers? In a paper published in 2023 the authors reviewed the experience gained from a selection of freshwater citizen science projects across Europe, particularly long-running projects, to identify key challenges and the supports required to sustain citizen engagement (Kelly-Quinn *et al.*, 2023). Their focus was on small water bodies as they saw significant data gaps that could be filled by well trained and supported citizen science projects. However, they noted that the framework proposed for operationalising citizen science in small water bodies was relevant to citizen science projects more generally. In this short piece I highlight some of the main take-home messages from the paper that may be particularly useful for new projects.

Citizen science has the potential to fill data gaps relating to small water bodies, in particular headwater streams.
Photo by Mary Kelly-Quinn

The proposed framework has five key attributes or steps that should be considered when developing citizen science projects. They are Project Establishment, Training of Volunteers, Data Acquisition and Interpretation/Reporting. Last but not least is Communication which is often an underestimated element of successful citizen science projects. Each has several associated tasks. However, a key starting point is to give thought to the purpose of a proposed citizen science project. It is generally agreed that the core focus should be data collection that addresses genuine scientific objectives. An added co-benefit, without doubt, is the potential of the project to increase societal awareness of the value of clean, healthy freshwaters and how human activities are degrading them together with the ecosystem services we depend on from those resources.

Key Take-home Messages

Effective co-ordination is required for sustained citizen science engagement.

This is particularly important for projects that envisage long-term or wide spatial collection of data and is key to sustained volunteer effort. The experience of long-running projects, such as those covered in the aforementioned paper, highlights the need for a defined organisation at national or regional level taking responsibility for overall coordination. Such a body would have oversight of the project's objectives and develop a strategy to enable a network of regional or local hubs, as well as addressing issues relating to site access, health and safety, data management and insurance.

Volunteers need to see that their efforts have a value. Therefore, project objectives should be well defined, and the data or information gaps being filled and use of the data needs to be communicated to potential volunteers. This, together with resources related to data storage training, systems for reporting and display of citizen science data as well as data validation procedures are key project establishment tasks.

Different levels of volunteer contribution can facilitate wider participation. Not all volunteers are available to make equal commitment to a project. It is, therefore, important to consider whether a project can accommodate variable inputs thus enabling wider participation. The authors note as an example the [Dragonfly Ireland project 2020-2024](#) that offered volunteers three levels of participation; *Spotters* who submit casual records; *Recorders* conduct timed surveys while *Monitors* conduct repeated surveys.

Male Beautiful Demoiselle damselfly (Calopteryx virgo).
Photo by Jan-Robert Baars.

Good training underpins data quality. Data collection for water quality or biodiversity monitoring schemes should be appropriate to the varying level of expertise of the volunteers and ideally provide for progression as interest, knowledge and skills develop. Some examples include the Citizen Science Stream Index (CSSI) and the Small Stream Impact Score (SSIS) in Ireland. CSSI is based on just six macroinvertebrate indicators at a high level of identification compared to the family level identification required by the SSIS. The Anglers' Riverfly Monitoring Initiative (ARMI) in the UK also offers various 'Riverfly Plus' packages with extended list of taxa

that provide a progression pathway for volunteers to broaden their identification skills as well as providing more in-depth information on the river sites.

Training therefore needs to be adjusted to the level of expertise required for the different schemes with bespoke training materials. Some of the training material could introduce children to life in our rivers and lakes and the concept of water pollution. It is, however, important to be cognisant of the amount of time required for training volunteers. This will clearly vary with the type of data collection. Training for field water chemistry testing or collection of samples for analysis by others is generally quite quick, but identification of, for example macroinvertebrate indicators takes many training sessions and refresher sessions before volunteers gain sufficient confidence. The challenge here is to enable sustained training effort for long-term projects and those that require high spatial coverage. A Training-of-Trainers approach whereby trained volunteers become trainers is a capacity building approach that is worth considering but requires considerable planning and effort by the project leaders.

Communication is a critical element of successful citizen science projects.

A communication strategy should ideally be co-developed with volunteers but also with the wider public. Communication between coordinators and volunteers, and between volunteers needs to be facilitated and where relevant this could be extended to groups or hubs in other parts of the country. This may help reduce attrition among volunteers. We should remember that volunteers need to see the fruits of their efforts and feedback of results is a key communication task. In terms of the wider public the project needs to be visible. This could be achieved through a website presence, regular blogs and social media. The challenge is to extend the awareness beyond the volunteers and others who are already environmentally conscious individuals. As noted by Kelly-Quinn *et al.* (2023) communication of the project goals and results to local stakeholders and the general public helps spark interest, and at the very least creates awareness and could promote wider volunteer engagement.

Heptageniid mayfly nymph, a key indicator taxon in citizen science indices. Illustration by Aoife Quinn

Is there a role for citizen science in freshwater quality and biodiversity monitoring? It is a definite yes from me, but the effort and resources required should not be underestimated.

Reference

Kelly-Quinn M, Biggs JN, Brooks S, Fortuno P, Hegarty S, Jones JI, Regan F. 2023. Opportunities, approaches and challenges to the engagement of citizens in filling small water body data gaps. *Hydrobiologia* 850: 3419-3439.

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